

Ten Horizon Europe projects are joining forces within the SUSTAFUELS Cluster to drive the next generation of sustainable algae-based fuels. By fostering cross-project innovation and collaboration, the cluster is enhancing technological breakthroughs, accelerating decarbonization pathways, and advancing a more circular and resilient transport system.

Collaborative approach across projects

ALFAFUELS, ALGAESOL, FUELGAE, SUNFUSION, SusAlgaeFuel and **SUSTEPS** aim to enhance the algae-based biofuel value chains by improving biomass productivity and its conversion into sustainable fuels.

These projects explore the **use of alternative carbon sources**, including captured CO₂ and waste-derived streams, to **support the production of renewable fuels for hard-to-abate transport sectors**, such as aviation and maritime transport, contributing to the replacement of fossil fuels with low-carbon alternatives.

ALGAESOL

ICARUS, COCPIT, CAPTUS and **NIAGARA** cover complementary segments of the sustainable fuels value chain, from carbon capture and biomass processing to fuel conversion.

By combining advanced CO₂ capture, innovative bioprocessing and conversion routes, and the use of waste-derived streams and sustainable cropping systems, they **contribute to improve energy efficiency and fuel performance**, supporting the development of scalable low-carbon fuel pathways.

Scan the QR code to read the press release on the cluster formation, and learn more about the projects by clicking the logos.

